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FAULT ATTACK ON AES & REDUCTION OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN NOC BY USING ENCODING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTARCT:

This paper mainly focuses on reducing the consumption of energy by the power dissipated links of a network on-chip (NoC - Network on Chip) which starts to compete with the power dissipated by the other elements of the communication subsystem like the routers and the network interfaces (NIs). It provides a set of data encoding and decoding schemes aimed at reducing the power dissipated by the links of a NoC. The proposed schemes are general and transparent with respect to the underlying NoC Architectures. The paper provides few techniques to overcome the power dissipation by self switching activity and coupling switching activity. The proposed schemes has been implemented on Xilinx FPGA of Spartan-6 Family and it shows that 51% of power dissipation and 14% of energy consumption is saved and 15% area overhead in the NI is achieved without affecting the performance

I INTRODUCTION

SHIFTING from a silicon technology node to the next technology results in faster and morepower efficient gates but slower and more power hungry wires [1]. In fact, more than 50% of the total dynamic power is dissipated in interconnects in current processors, and this is expected to rise to 65%–80% over the next several years [2]. Global interconnect length does not scale with smaller transistors and local wires. Chip size remains relatively constant because the function of the continues to increase and RC delay increases exponentially. At 32/28 nm, for instance, the RC delay in a 1-mm global wire at the minimum pitch is 25× higher than the intrinsic delay of a two-input NAND fanout of 5 [3]. If the raw computation horsepower seems to be unlimited, thanks to the ability of instancing more and more cores in a single silicon die, scalability issues.

II. OVERVIEW OF THE PROPOSAL

The basic idea of the proposed approach is encoding the flits before they are injected into the network with the goal of minimizing the self-switching activity and the coupling switching activity in the links traversed by the flits. In fact, self-switching activity and coupling switching activity are responsible for link power dissipation. In this paper, we refer to the end-to-end scheme. This end-to-end encoding technique takes advantage of the pipeline nature of the wormhole switching technique. Note that since the same sequence of flits passes through all the links of the routing path, the encoding decision taken at the NI may provide the same power saving for all the links. For the proposed scheme, an encoder and a decoder block are added to the NI. Except for the header flit, the encoder encodes the outgoing flits of the packet such that the power dissipated by the inter-router point-to-point link is minimized. This end-to-end encoding technique takes advantage of the pipeline nature of the wormhole switching technique. Change of transition types on effect of odd inversion In addition, the scheme was based on the hop-by-hop technique, and Hence, encoding/decoding is performed in each node. The scheme presented indeed with reducing the coupling switching. In this method, a complex encoder counts the number of Type I (Table I) transitions with a weighting coefficient of one and the number of Type II transitions with the weighting coefficient of two. If the number is larger than half of the to the complex encoder, the technique only works on the patterns whose full inversion leads to the link power reduction while not considering the patterns whose full inversions may lead to higher link power consumption. Therefore, the link power reduction achieved through this technique is not as large as it could be. This scheme was also based on the hop-by-hop technique. In another coding technique presented in, groups of four bits each are encoded with five bits. The encoded bits were isolated using shielding wires such that the occurrence of the patterns “101” and “010” were prevented. This way, no simultaneous Type II transitions in two adjacent pair bits are induced. This technique effectively reduces the coupling switching activity. Although the technique reduces the power consumption considerably, it increases the data transfer time, and hence, the link energy consumption. This is due to the fact that for each four bits, six bits are transmitted which increases the communication traffic. This technique was also based on the hop-by-hop technique. A coding technique that reduces the coupling switching

activity by taking the advent age of end-to-end encoding for wormhole switching has been presented in. It is based on lowering the coupling switching activity by eliminating only Type II transitions. In this paper, we present three encoding schemes. In Scheme I, we focus on reducing Type I transitions while in Scheme II, both Types I and II transitions are taken into account for deciding between half and full invert, depending the amount of switching reduction. Finally, in Scheme III, we consider the fact that Type I transitions show different behaviors in the case of odd and even inverts and make the inversion which leads to the higher power saving.

III PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this section, we present the proposed encoding scheme whose goal is to reduce power dissipation by minimizing the coupling transition activities on the links of the interconnection network. A. Scheme I In scheme I, we focus on reducing the numbers of Type I transitions (by converting them to Types III and IV transitions) and Type II transitions (by converting them to Type I transition). The scheme compares the current data with the previous one to decide whether odd inversion or no inversion of the current data can lead to the link power reduction.

1) **Power Model:** If the flit is odd inverted before being transmitted, the dynamic power on the link is $P \propto T^0 \rightarrow 1 + (K_1 T^1 + K_2 T^2 + K_3 T^3 + K_4 T^4) C_c(1)$ where $T^0 \rightarrow 1$, T^1 , T^2 , T^3 , and T^4 , are the selftransition activity, and the coupling transition activity of Types I, II, III, and IV, respectively. Table I reports, for each transition, the relationship between the coupling transition activities of the flit when transmitted as is and when its bits are odd inverted. Internal view of the encoder block This presents the condition used to determine whether the odd inversion has to be performed or not.

2) **Proposed Encoding Architecture:** The proposed encoding architecture, which is based on the odd invert condition defined is shown in Fig. 1. We consider a link width of w bits. If no encoding is used, the body flits are grouped in w bits by the NI and are transmitted via the link. In our approach, one bit of the link is used for the inversion bit, which indicates if the flit traversing the link has been inverted or not. More specifically, the NI packs the body flits in $w - 1$ bits. The encoding logic E, which is integrated into the NI, is responsible for deciding if the inversion should take place and performing the inversion if needed. The decoder circuit simply

inverts the received flit when the inversion bit is high. B. Scheme II In the proposed encoding scheme II, we make use of both odd (as discussed previously) and full inversion. The full inversion operation converts Type II transitions to Type IV transitions. The scheme compares the current data with the previous one to decide whether the odd, full, or no inversion of the current data can give rise to the link power reduction. 1) Power Model: Let us indicate with P , P' , and P'' the power dissipated by the link when the flit is transmitted with no inversion, odd inversion, and full inversion, respectively. The odd inversion leads to power reduction when $P' < P''$ and $P' < P$. The power P'' is given by $P'' \propto T_1 + 2T_4^{**}$ (2) Neglecting the self-switching activity, we obtain the condition $P' < T_1 + 2T_4^{**}$ (3) Therefore, using (2) and (3), we can write $2(T_2 - T_4^{**}) > 2(T_1 - T_4^{**})$ (4) Volume 4, Issue 2 JULY 2015 IJRAET Similarly, the condition for the full inversion is obtained from $P'' < P$ and $P'' < P'$. The inequality $P'' < P$ is satisfied. $T_2 > T_4^{**}$ (6) Fig. 2 Encoder architecture of scheme II Therefore the full inversion condition is obtained as $2(T_2 - T_4^{**}) > 2(T_1 - T_4^{**})$ (7) When none of (6) or (7) is satisfied, no inversion will be performed. 2) Proposed Encoding Architecture: The operating principles of this encoder are similar to those of the encoder implementing Scheme I. The proposed encoding architecture, which is based on the odd invert condition of (6) and the full invert condition of (7), is shown in Fig.2 Here again, the w th bit of the previously and the full invert condition of (7) is shown in Fig. 2 Here again, the w th bit of the previously encoded body flit is indicated with inv which defines if it was odd or full inverted ($inv = 1$) or left as it was ($inv = 0$). (a) Circuit Diagram (b) Internal Part of Decoder

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed data encoding schemes have been assessed by means of a cycle-accurate NoC simulator based on Noxim. The power estimation models of Noxim include NIs, routers, and links. was computed using (3) where the terms $T_0 \rightarrow 1$, T_1 , and T_2 were computed based on the information obtained from the cycle accurate simulation. The following parameters were used in the simulations. The NoC was clocked at 700 MHz while the baseline NI with minimum buffering and supporting open core protocol 2 and advanced high-performance bus protocols dissipated 5.3 mW. The average power dissipated by the wormhole-based router was 5.7 mW. Based on a 65-nm UMC technology, a total capacitance of 592 fF/mm was assumed for

an inter-router wire. About 80% of this capacitance was due to the crosstalk. We assumed 2-mm 32-bit links and a packet size of 16 bytes (eight flits). Using the detailed simulations, when the flits traversed the NoC links, the corresponding self and coupling switching activities were calculated and used along with the self- and coupling capacitance of 0.237 and 0.947 nf, respectively, to calculate the power ($V_{dd} = 0.9$ V and $F_{ck} = 700$ MHz). data encoding schemes aimed at reducing the power dissipated by the links of a NoC. In fact, links are responsible for a significant fraction of the overall power dissipated by the communication system. In addition, their contribution is expected to increase in future technology nodes. As compared to the previous encoding schemes proposed in the literature, the rationale behind the proposed schemes is to minimize not only the switching activity, but also (and in particular) the coupling switching activity which is mainly responsible for link power dissipation in the deep submicrometer technology regime.

V CONCLUSION

The proposed encoding schemes are agnostic with respect to the underlying NoC architecture in the sense that their application does not require any modification neither in the routers nor in the links. An extensive evaluation has been carried out to assess the impact of the encoder and decoder logic in the NI. The encoders implementing the proposed schemes have been assessed in terms of power dissipation and silicon area. The impacts on the performance, power, and energy metrics have been studied using a cycle- and bit accurate NoC simulator under both synthetic and real traffic scenarios. Overall, the application of the proposed encodingschemes allows reduced no. of transitions from scheme-I to scheme-II & Scheme-II to Scheme-III which reduces power consumption as well as area also.

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